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Definition of Data Quality Metrics

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R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

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PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Abbreviations and definitions

The abbreviations and definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [[ref](#)].

Executive Summary

Reusing poor quality data has limited value. When developing the requirements for the AIDAVA curation virtual assistant, data users repeatedly asked the same question: how reliable the data is. The answer differs depending on the state of the data: i) for data sources, a quality label can be established based on the quality level provided by the data holder — if available — including the credentials of the persons who created and validated the data; ii) for the curated data (i.e. the PHKG), the quality label will be linked to the quality from the source, the level of quality and certification of the curation tools used during transformation, the level of health and literacy of the humans who provided answers when there were semantic gaps, and the number of data quality checks that could not be resolved; iii) for published data, the quality label will be linked to the level of the curated data, the compliance with the target format, the completeness of the content, the absence of bias as well as the quality, reliability and certification of the imputation algorithm, if applicable.

This document provides a detailed overview of AIDAVA deliverable 4.6, focusing on data quality and metadata across the health data life cycle. This deliverable serves as a key component in AIDAVA, aimed at developing a comprehensive data quality assessment methodology. This methodology is crucial for ensuring the reliability, transparency, and effective reuse of health data. The document highlights the importance of maintaining high standards of health data quality and incorporates data quality dimensions, methodologies, and tools. Furthermore, deliverable 4.6 is linked with other integral parts of the project, namely deliverables 1.3 (Business requirements for R1) [1], 1.4 (Definition of assessment study including test scenarios & metrics, and study initiation package) [2], 2.1 (Global data sharing standard) [3], and 2.2 (Details on data curation & publishing process) (deliverable on request). These deliverables introduce SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) rules and specific data quality guidelines, contributing for establishing data quality practices.

1. Introduction and objectives

1.1. Scope and content of a data quality framework

The main goal of AIDAVA is to deliver a universal semantic representation of an interoperable and reusable patient longitudinal health record that is curated from multiple heterogeneous data sources and that can be reused for multiple purpose, by the patients and their treating physicians in clinical care or shared – with the consent of the patient – for clinical research. As there is limited value in reusing and sharing low-quality data, AIDAVA emphasises the importance of data quality. By upholding specific data quality instruments, AIDAVA ensures that the resulting longitudinal health record is both trustworthy and insightful, thereby enhancing its usability and impact in clinical settings and research activities.

Data quality is a wide topic with multiple facets. In the context of AIDAVA, we identified 4 aspects that needed to be covered, as displayed in the figure below:

1. Data Quality dimensions, which have been widely described in the literature and allow structuring the approach to data quality; they are further described in Section 2.2
2. Instruments of data quality, including data quality life cycle, metadata, quality check and quality labels. Identification and implementation of these different instruments is the core of the document. They are described in Section 2.3
3. Objectives of data quality which clarifies the purpose of checking quality on a dataset. A data quality level of 100% is rarely achievable, and it is important to identify the primary purpose for checking data quality. Indeed, the objective of data quality assessment would typically be different for clinical care (single patient level) than for research purposes (at population level). This is described in Section 2.5
4. Cost of non-quality is another important component to measure. There is a cost to control data quality; equally, there is a cost of non-quality. When deciding on how far to measure quality, both aspects must be considered.

Figure 1. The different components of the AIDAVA quality framework

The objective of Task 4.2 is to define and implement the different instruments identified in Figure 1 and to apply them across the agreed dimensions, to meet the objective of the AIDAVA project i.e. deliver high-quality data at the different stages of data life cycle (raw data, curated data, and published data).

While applying the different instruments, the project will consider the cost of measuring quality versus the cost of non-quality; indeed, in certain situations the cost of measuring quality is higher than the risk and cost of non-quality. For instance, in AIDAVA, we should check the data quality of raw data sources to ensure it is worth integrating a specific source data into the patient longitudinal health record; an incorrect data source may otherwise create an unnecessary burden in the checking of inconsistencies and errors, or worst, be responsible for an incorrect personal record. Ideally, we should have data quality information about the data source coming from the data holder. This is however not readily available in most places, and it would be extremely difficult to obtain this information for the AIDAVA project. This information is not critical to the success of the project, as the resulting data will not be used for actual decision-making. We therefore concluded that the cost of measuring the quality of data sources would outweigh the risk and cost of non-quality.

In AIDAVA, the evaluation of data quality for data sources is therefore limited to checking the conformance to the data transfer specification and mandatory metadata. If AIDAVA were implemented in production, with impact on medical decision-making, this would need to be reconsidered.

As the objective of AIDAVA is to automate curation and publishing of heterogeneous data, the data quality framework in AIDAVA is focusing on 2 aspects:

- Data quality dimensions
- Instruments of data quality

1.2. The need for data quality in EHDS

The emerging European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation will heavily impact the way we manage health data. Hence, instruments to ensure data quality are critically important in the implementation of the regulation. The regulation was submitted for public consultation in May 2022. Comments from the European Parliament were submitted in November and from the Council in December 2023. Assuming final consultations with member states move forward smoothly, officials from the European Commission hope for a final approval of the regulation by the second quarter of 2024.

In EHDS, data quality is mentioned in the recitals, and within two chapters within the core regulation. In Chapter III on electronic health record systems (where EHRs are taken in their wide sense, not just hospital systems), Article 23 mentions that EHRs common specification should include requirements related to data quality, without further details. In Chapter IV on secondary data use, Section 5, Article 56 describes in more detail the composition of a 'data quality and utility label'.

The regulation remains by its nature high level; implementing acts that will be derived to support implementation of the EHDS should include more detailed specification on data quality verification and validation.

TEHDAS, the Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space, focused in Deliverable 6.1 on recommendations for a data quality framework (DQFs). However, the project only considers datasets for secondary use in the context of cross-border sharing; it recommends clarifying the objective of data quality (i.e. "fitness for purpose"), to implement five measurable dimensions of data quality and to publish metadata on secondary datasets including information on data provenance, relevance, and coverage. Deliverable 6.3 expands on these recommendations toward implementation of data quality and utility labels for secondary datasets as specified in EHDS Article 56.

Within AIDAVA, the focus is on measuring data quality of curated collected data. The working hypothesis of the project is that it is more effective to curate data at the source, at patient level, and ensure data quality at that level. Indeed, if patient data are integrated and of high quality, the cost to derive secondary datasets fit for purpose and of high quality should dramatically decrease. This deliverable will conclude with recommendations to be considered in the implementing acts of the EHDS, that should complement the recommendations from the TEHDAS project

2. Description of activities

2.1. Reviews of external initiatives and AIDAVA business requirements

2.1.1. Review of EHDS – data quality for data sources – what are the requirements?

Article 23.3(c) of the EHDS [4] requires that any electronic health data must be accompanied by a statement that describes the data's quality, specifically its completeness and accuracy.

In alignment to the regulation in the EHDS data holders shall make their data available for secondary use purposes. This gives them a responsibility towards data preparation for further use of health data. Data holders will be required to try in data preparation, necessitating the adoption of data quality management and assurance protocols. While registries typically operate under strict protocols and guidelines, ensuring that data is meticulously collected, curated, and maintained, the same principle of data quality management must now be integrated to routine health data collection environments, such as electronic health records (EHRs).

Article 56 of the EHDS [4] outlines obligatory compliance with specific requirements for data holders sharing their data, including:

- (Meta-)data documentation regarding data models, data dictionary, standards used, provenance, ...
- Technical quality, providing information on certain data quality dimensions (e.g. completeness, uniqueness, accuracy, validity, timeliness, and consistency of the data).
- Level of maturity of the data quality management processes, including review and audit processes.
- Coverage of the provided data (e.g., representativity of population sampled, average timeframe in which a natural person appears in dataset).
- Information on access and provision, time between the collection of the health data and their addition to the dataset, time to provide electronic health data following electronic health data access application approval.

- Information on data enrichments: merging and adding data to an existing dataset, including links with other datasets.

While not all these facets may be directly tackled by AIDAVA, the project recognizes the critical importance of adhering to the EHDS requirements. To facilitate compliance and elevate the standard of health data quality, AIDAVA is committed to establishing a feedback loop with data holders. This feedback loop will establish a continuous enhancement of data quality management for data holders.

2.1.2. FAIRification

FAIR Data principles [5] are intended to improve the reusability and efficacy of data-driven research and decision-making. AIDAVA's mission is to enhance the quality, interoperability, and reusability of health data, which FAIRification plays a crucial role in. FAIRification refers to transforming data into a format that aligns with the FAIR principles. By standardising data formats, FAIRification makes sharing data across different platforms and entities easier. By implementing FAIRification, the project ensures that health data is not only standardised but also enriched semantically, making it more valuable and reusable.

The FAIRification process, as described by Jacobsen et al. [6], encompasses a set of steps for converting existing data into its FAIR version. After retrieving non-FAIR data from its sources, the process starts with analysing datasets to understand their structures and alignment with domain concepts and semantic modelling. The next phase is to harmonise and add semantics, demanding models compliant with FAIR principles. Once data aligns with semantic definitions, it is transformed into a semantic-rich format and enriched with metadata. Finally, the FAIRified data is stored in a way that ensures easy discovery and accessibility.

2.1.3. Review of existing data quality frameworks

To face the multiple challenges within our healthcare system, the secondary use of health data holds multiple advantages. But because of concerns about the quality of the data being used, healthcare is not obtaining the full potential of the secondary use of health data. High-quality data is essential for reliable analysis and decision-making. To be considered high-quality, data must exhibit some key characteristics such as being complete, accurate, and current. These characteristics are known as data quality dimensions. Over time, literature has endeavoured to create frameworks that capture these dimensions in detail [7-9].

Despite these efforts, the health data sector still lacks a comprehensive framework that addresses all aspects of data quality, particularly for secondary usage [10]. This has led to a fragmented understanding of data quality dimensions, with varying interpretations depending on the context. Moreover, the health data field faces challenges in developing robust methods to assess data quality. The literature suggests that existing methods are often constrained by the absence of standardised metrics that can accurately assess data quality across different dimensions. This limitation also extends to the transformation of these dimensions into concrete criteria for primary and secondary usage, as well as for the extract, transformation, load (ETL) processes that consider the original intent being the data's collection.

2.1.4. Requests from the users related to data quality

As part of Task 1.3. Business Requirements [1] (see Deliverable 1.3 - Business Requirements for G1, Section 3.7), the project identified a set of requirements. These requirements were categorised in epics and prioritised by severity (blocking, major, minor). The table below provides the requirements and acceptance criteria identified in D1.3 and related to data quality; for each acceptance criteria, we added how the criterion will be implemented through the data quality instruments, as specified in Figure 1 and documented in this deliverable. Several requirements/criteria mandate human interactions and or display through the AIDAVA prototype; in this case we specify the AIDAVA module where the requirement will be implemented.

Req ID	Requirement	Severity	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion	Data quality instruments
C0289	As an expert curator willing to check the curated data in AIDAVA, I want to be able to see how the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant came up with certain information or where it found certain information (e.g. size of the tumour or TNM-staging) so that I can understand exactly what was going on every step of the way and I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant.	major	AC0289.1	The system provides the curator the option to see where the date/information originates from.	Metadata
			AC0289.2	On demand of the curator, the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant displays where an information/datum comes from (database or system or device or app etc).	Metadata
C0292	As an expert curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want to change my response in case of an error / a mistake so that I can have support from the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to guide with a more correct answer; the changes I made must be logged.	major	AC0292.1	The system automatically runs quality checks - during the curation process - according to the defined quality rules.	Data Quality Checks
			AC0292.2	When the system recognises a breach of any quality rule applicable, the system fires an alert and asks the user to correct the error. Then the system stores the answer with traceability in the PHKG.	Data Quality Checks
			AC0292.3	In G1 - the question to the user is predefined. In G2 - the system provides more contextual information to support the user	Data Quality Checks
C0293	As a data user willing to check the data delivered from AIDAVA, I want to have access to some agreed parameters (anonymised statistics) computed out of	major	AC0293.1	The system computes statistical parameters from the log files. (Note: predefined parameters is to be defined)	Data Quality Labels

Req ID	Requirement	Severity	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion	Data quality instruments
	the log files so that I can have details for the validation process.		AC0293.2	The user has access to those statistics computed by the AIDAVA tool in a predefined table.	Data Quality Labels
C0294	As a data user, when considering accessing medical data through AIDAVA, I want to know what kind of quality checks have been done so that I will have access to high quality data.	major	AC0294.1	The system provides information about the quality checks performed on the accessed medical data.	Data Quality Checks
C0295	As a data user when making sure that I can trust the data, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to measure the quality of the data so that I see that it has been validated according to certain standard criteria when data have been entered to the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant and no errors in future treatment plans will be made based on the available data.	major	AC0295.1	The system incorporates mechanisms to measure and assess the quality of data upon entry into the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant.	Data Quality Checks
			AC0295.2	(Upon request by the data user) the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant provides information about how data has been validated according to established criteria upon entry into the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant.	Data Quality Checks
C0296	As a data user when making sure that the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant delivers the right data, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to automatically measure the quality of the data based on certain standards so that I can make the right decisions and the next physician who will see the patient can make correct decisions as well.	major	AC0296.1	The system automatically measures the quality of the data based on predefined standards.	Data Quality Checks
C0297	As a patient ingesting medical data into AIDAVA, I want to have safeguarding checks in place to recognize whether the data/information was input correctly, and the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant shall tell me to review this information when there are obvious mistakes (e.g. when mistakenly uploaded a health document from another person) so that I can review and correct the mistake.	major	AC0297.1	The system recognizes automatically if the ingested data by a user belongs to a different person.	Data Quality Checks
		major	AC0297.2	The system alerts the user and asks for review of the ingested data when it recognizes data ingested belongs to a different person.	Data Quality Checks

Req ID	Requirement	Severity	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion	Data quality instruments
C0298	As a patient using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want to check (on demand) what the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant has done when automatically curating my data and the quality of the curated data and who has accessed it so that I can be sure that data curation is working correctly, and the data are of high quality.	major	AC0298.1	When showing a Data Quality Labels, the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant provides an easy-to-understand description of the criteria of the Data Quality Labels, including the validation rules, and what AIDAVA has done to improve the quality.	Data Quality Labels
			AC0298.2	The system shows on user's demand the quality label of the source data and the respective curated data.	Data Quality Labels
			AC0298.3	The system shows on user's demand the source data and the respective curated data.	Metadata
C0290	As an expert curator willing to check the curated data in AIDAVA, I want to be able to do random checks on the curated data (e.g. check difference between source data and curated data) so that I can see if the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant has problems to curate certain kind of data or information.	minor	AC0290.1	The system provides the curator the option to see the original source (document) of the data (to compare (e.g. side by side) the source data and the curated data).	Metadata
			AC0290.2	On demand of the curator, the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant display the original source (document) of the data.	Metadata
C0291	As an expert curator using automatic data curation in AIDAVA, I want the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant to check for when a report on a comparison between radiologic images is made in the ingested data and throw an alert if the compared images were not taken within a month from each other and are actually not comparable so that images that have been taken too far apart are not wrongly compared with each other.	minor	AC0291.1	The system realises if the radiology report includes a comparison of 2 images of a tumour in the context of breast cancer.	Data Quality Checks
			AC0291.2	The system identifies if there is a period of more than 30 days between the 2 images compared.	Data Quality Checks
			AC0291.3	The system notifies the user that there was an issue comparing radiologic images (=more than 30 days in between the images' dates).	Data Quality Checks
C0215	As a patient and as a curator helping AIDAVA with manual data curation, I want to get information on how confident the data XY is in the knowledge graph so that I can trust the AIDAVA health data curation and publishing virtual assistant.	major	AC0215.1	For data items, which were retrieved/curated by AI tools, the KG stores confidence information as well as the source of this confidence information.	Metadata

Req ID	Requirement	Severity	Acceptance Criterion ID	Acceptance Criterion	Data quality instruments
			AC0215.2	The system provides the patient and the expert curator the option to ask for the confidence of a data item in the KG. (e.g. by clicking a "confidence information" button).	Data Quality Labels
			AC0215.3	The confidence information for a data item in the KG is displayed to the patient and the expert curator on demand.	Data Quality Labels

2.2. Data quality dimensions used in AIDAVA

A recent review [10] provides a comprehensive analysis of the quality of health data for secondary use, outlining various frameworks and methods for assessing data quality as reported in the literature. Building on this foundation, researchers synthesised numerous definitions to identify 9 core dimensions of data quality, as defined by the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i~HD). This framework highlights the 9 most critical dimensions for evaluating the integrity of health data when repurposed for secondary use.

Figure 2. European Institute for Innovation through Health data quality framework

Dimensions	Definitions	Comments
Completeness	Data values are present when they would be expected.	Blank fields that are not expected (e.g. the entry of a date of death when the patient did not die) are not regarded as missing data but rather as incorrect data.
Consistency	<u>By type</u> : All data values are examined to verify if they are in the right format (numerical, categorical, date, character), as defined in the data dictionary.	When no restrictions are formulated regarding value format, the resulting data quality errors and labels must be left blank ("NA"), since there could be no consistency error of consistency to a value format that has not been specified.
	<u>By range</u> : Examine whether numerical values fall within pre-specified ranges and whether categorical/character variables have values that comply with predefined response options as described in the data dictionary.	When no restrictions are formulated regarding response range, errors and labels are left blank ("NA").
	<u>By multivariate rules</u> : Examine whether violations to data quality, interdependence relationships that are defined between different variables.	/
Correctness	Values are true and unbiased with respect to their real-world state.	A value can be consistent but incorrect, but a value cannot be inconsistent and correct.

Dimensions	Definitions	Comments
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By combining information across variables (i.e., multivariate correctness). - Over time (i.e., longitudinal correctness). 	
Uniqueness	Records representing a single patient are not replicated.	Three different types of uniqueness: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of completely duplicated data rows. - Identical visit identifier in the patient visits records, even though values of one or more data items might have different values. - Multiple identical data in the patient visit records while the visit identifier differs.
Stability	Relates to the probabilistic concordance of data among different sources (e.g., hospitals, physicians, or devices) or over time.	Results will be distorted when multi-site or longitudinal variability is not properly considered.
Timeliness	Extent to which information is up-to-date for a task. And if the output is available on time.	/
Contextualisation	The process of adding related information to data to make it more meaningful/useful.	Without annotation of the acquisition context, data might not be interpretable.
Representativeness	The extent to which a dataset reflects the target population.	This is important to allow valid inference.
Trustworthiness	The extent to which information is regarded as true and credible.	Data can be trusted, based on the reputation of the stakeholders and institutions involved in the acquisition of data.

This framework is unique for two main reasons. Firstly, it integrates nine core dimensions of data quality into a single, unified model. This consolidation means that various dimensions identified across different frameworks, which are aimed at secondary uses of health data, can be mapped with the ones specified in our chosen framework. Secondly, the framework is designed with flexibility in mind, making it possible for us to customise the definitions and requirements according to the specific needs of each point in the data's life cycle. This adaptability is crucial as it allows for precision in applying the framework to diverse projects, ensuring that data quality is maintained consistently across AIDAVA's operations.

While each of these 9 dimensions play a vital role in ensuring data quality, we have chosen to focus our efforts in this deliverable on 2 specific data quality dimensions (completeness and consistency). The decision to exclude these 7 other dimensions from the current deliverable is not a matter of their significance. Rather, it reflects the focus of a key data quality aspect defined in the beginning of the project, the importance of semantic consistency and completeness. It is important to consider the dynamic nature of health data quality and its requirements, therefore we remain open to the possibility of including these dimensions if future research within this project and engagement with different stakeholders reveal their importance in improving the level of data quality.

2.3. Data quality instruments needed in AIDAVA

2.3.1. Data Life cycle

By design, the AIDAVA prototype is managing personal data through different levels as described in the figure below, from collected data transferred from the source holders (level 1) to a published format serving a specific purpose (level 4).

Figure 3. Data Journey in AIDAVA with different levels from collected data (level 1) to derived/published data (level 4).

A clear definition of these 4 levels is critical, as data quality will be measured differently for each level. This allows the project to distinguish itself from traditional one-time, single-point data quality assessments, by adopting a proactive approach that involves performing multiple data quality assessments at critical stages throughout the entire data journey and allows identifying and address potential data quality issues at the level they arise.

Deliverable 6.3 of the TEHDAS project proposes a different data life cycle, as described in the figure below.

- It includes both the data preparation and reuse phases
- The data preparation phase is focusing on population data from the data collection onwards i.e. needed data are extracted - across patients - from the data sources, standardised (or curated) and then published as a FAIR dataset, supporting retrieval, sharing and reuse.

AIDAVA focuses on the data preparation phase only and works at SINGLE patient level, rather than at population level. The working hypothesis of the project is that it is more effective to harmonise data across different data sources, at patient level (curate once, use many times) than across each extract of data from a population of patients (curate many times, use once). Indeed, once data have been harmonised at patient level, they can be reused for multiple secondary uses at population level

Figure 4. TEHDAS Data life cycle

Within AIDAVA, data quality will be checked following relevant dimensions at each level identified in Figure 3 and will result in a Data Quality Labels. This label will be computed for the current situation (G0) whenever relevant, for the first generation of the prototype (G1, targeted for July 2024) and for the second generation of the prototype (G2, targeted for March 2026).

2.3.2. Metadata

The term metadata is widely but variably used to describe information properties that do and/or should accompany data items of core interest to a community of data creators and users. There are several kinds of metadata that capture different essential contexts to enable the core data items to be correctly interpreted, trusted, used, and shared. In AIDAVA we must ensure we have metadata that includes sufficient context information to ensure that any future user of the data (whether at single patient level or analysing data sets) can be confident about where the data have come from and the context in which it originated, and what transformations have been undertaken from the source to the point of use.

AIDAVA has identified several categories of metadata to support different requirements and stages in the data processing workflow: data collection, data source onboarding and mapping to the AIDAVA reference ontology to enable automation, information on data lineage (i.e. information on all steps that took place in the transformation of a data item, from data source onwards) on any data output from AIDAVA. The metadata were identified independently across the different teams; in parallel, the data quality team described a categorization of metadata, introduced below. These categories were used to align all the previously defined metadata into a consistent set, to be used across the AIDAVA virtual assistant for potentially different purposes.

Metadata applicable to individual data items, data item clusters or larger units of EHR information relating to a single patient

- Metadata to be extracted and preserved from the data source.
 - **Care context metadata**, documenting where and why care was provided e.g. if the documented care was an emergency visit, a new presentation, or a follow-up or a screening visit, was part of a package of care delivered by one member of a multi-professional team, was an instalment along a care pathway etc.

- **Creation metadata** relating to the time, place, person origination of the data source, including history and the chaining of versions.
- **Data representation metadata** relating to schema/data dictionary of the data source, and to mapping information.
- Metadata to be created throughout transformation and curation within AIDAVA; this metadata should be following the W3C standard on provenance.
 - **Computer traceability metadata** capturing the transformations to the source data applied through the AIDAVA pipeline, including the version specific specification of what rules, software, execution engines and validations were used for each transformation.
 - **Human curator traceability metadata** capturing the view of the PHKG that was shared with curators (e.g. patients), metadata capturing the data item changes advocated by the curator and comments made by the curator as annotator remarks on the data.
- Metadata applicable to individual (patient level) data extracts (e.g. IPS) generated from the individual PHKG and stored with the published output.
 - **Individual extract generation metadata**, e.g. relating to the time point snapshot of the PHKG at which generation occurred, and other relevant criteria that were applied to derive the extract.
 - **Individual technical metadata** with technical specification – through a schema – on the different data elements included in the extract, supporting smoother reuse.
 - **Individual extract access metadata**, capturing and preserving information about who can access the individual extract, when, how (which will be out of scope within AIDAVA).

Metadata applicable to data sets relating to multiple patients and stored with the generated dataset

- Data set generation
 - **Data set generation metadata**, e.g. relating to the time point snapshot of the PHKG at which generation occurred, patient and data item selection criteria that were applied to derive the data set.
 - **FAIR metadata** relating to data set discovery, access, and reusability.
- Data set utilisation
 - **Data set generation metadata** with technical specification – through a schema – on the different data elements included in the data sets, supporting smoother regeneration on demand, and reuse.
 - **Data set access metadata**, capturing and preserving information about access to, or provision of, data sets to third parties, including to whom, when, how, and any agreed permitted purpose for using the data.

The above categories have been distinguished because they will contain different information, will be populated at different points in the AIDAVA data flows, and will be of interest to different downstream data users, in particular distinguishing patient use and data reuse needs.

There are other kinds of metadata that may be applicable to health information, which are not discussed here because they are not pertinent to the mission and intended processing of AIDAVA.

These categories of metadata are discussed in more detail in a later chapter of this deliverable, including available standards that could/should be considered to implement this metadata. The technical specification of each needed metadata is provided, with their use in the AIDAVA data life cycle and their storage mechanism from a data quality perspective, the main dimensions of quality that are important here are completeness and consistency: for metadata properties that are mandatory, a value should always be present. Optional metadata properties need not always have a value. Every value provided must conform to the data dictionary (information representation and semantics) defined for that property. The other data quality dimensions, applicable to the values of the core data items, that are described in the next chapter of this document are not applicable to metadata.

2.3.3. Data Quality Checks

Data Quality Checks offer a simple mechanism to identify quality issues in data values and data records. They ensure that data meets predefined quality standards and is fit for its intended use. A Data Quality Check is a specific and well-defined condition used to assess the quality of data. It serves as a guideline or standard against which the data is measured to determine its completeness, consistency, and other relevant data quality dimensions.

Data Quality Checks are typically formulated based on domain-specific requirements and may vary over time or over projects. These rules can be simple or complex, depending on the complexity of the data and the objectives of the data quality assessment.

Dimension	Example of Data Quality Checks
Completeness	Completeness for all variables, except for the variable <i>use of insulin pump</i> . This variable can only be complete if variable <i>types of diabetes treatment</i> equals insulin.
Consistency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>By type</u>: A format has been defined for all variables, against which their consistency (by type) can be evaluated. ● <u>By range</u>: Height variable between 10–300 cm. ● <u>By multivariate rule</u>: Year of diagnose =< Date of birth

Definition, validation of Data Quality Checks in consensus with a community of experts require potentially a major effort; fortunately, several projects and/or initiatives have developed Data Quality Checks. Within AIDAVA and this deliverable, the focus is on a novel mechanism to implement and govern Data Quality Checks, rather than on generating new content. The project is therefore reusing existing Data Quality Checks which have already been validated in the literature or in other projects.

One difficulty in reusing Data Quality Checks is the format of the data on which these rules must be checked. In the data life cycle described above, data is stored in 3 different formats:

- Raw data source format for Level 1,
- Resource Description Framework (RDF) format constrained by the AIDAVA reference ontology for Level 2 and Level 3,

- Any requested format for Level 4.

As mentioned above, it is not possible for AIDAVA to check data quality of source data in their original format (Level 1), as this would mandate implementation of the Data Quality Check for each different format/data source. However, once source data are transformed into an RDF format constrained by the AIDAVA ontology (Level 2), the same Data Quality Checks can be reused across all data sources. At Level 3, integrating multiple data sources in RDF, the same rules can also be reused.

Data Quality Checks implemented for Level 2 and Level 3 refer to the AIDAVA reference ontology (see Deliverable 2.1 Global Data Sharing standard [3]) describing the SHKG and PHKG data, stored RDF format; they will be implemented through Shapes Constraints Language (SHACL), a standards-based framework that provides a machine-readable specification of Data Quality Checks integrated into the RDF framework. A SHACL validator can evaluate the data against constraints and report any violations, enabling to automate identification of data quality issues and supporting improvement of the overall quality of the RDF data. A detailed description of the implementation of SHACL constraints is provided in Section 3.2

It is important to note that the data format for level 4 will differ from the RDF used in level 2 and 3. While this document outlines Data Quality Checks tailored for RDF implementation in levels 2 and 3, it does not extend to the specifics of applying these rules to level 4. Due to the current time constraints, the application and evaluation of these rules for level 4 are beyond the scope of this deliverable. Addressing this will be a critical task to be undertaken after the present deadline.

2.3.4. Data Quality Labels

Establishing a Data Quality Labels is essential to provide a clear measure of the trustworthiness of the data. This step reflects AIDAVA's dedication to maintaining high-quality standards, from data collection to curation, ensuring the data's trustworthiness for effective healthcare decisions and advanced research.

The Data Quality Labels mechanism will play a vital role in AIDAVA towards:

- **Data sharing and reuse**
 - Objective assessment and transparency. The Data Quality Labels delivers an unbiased evaluation of the data against specific quality dimensions, such as completeness and consistency. This not only fosters transparency across all user groups but also builds trust in the data's capability to be reused in clinical and research applications.
 - Quality control. This scoring system provides detailed insights into each stage of data handling with AIDAVA. It functions as a quantitative indicator that monitors potential data quality issues.
- **Benchmarking and standardisation**

A standardised approach to scoring or labelling delineates explicit quality benchmarks. It harmonises expectations and results, facilitating the integration and comparison of data from disparate sources and institutions.
- **Guidance for improvement**

The Data Quality Labels is a navigational guide in the continuous journey to enhance data quality.
- **Regulatory compliance**

In alignment with the European Health Data space (EHDS) regulations, specifically articles 23 and 56, health data must possess a data quality and utility label, underscoring the adherence to certain standards.

Creating an effective visualisation for data quality across AIDAVA's processes is pivotal. Such a strategy must not only simplify complex quality metrics into comprehensible visuals but also spotlight the progressive enhancements achieved at each phase: from data source through the integration and curation of health data. This visual articulation is fostering transparent communication among all stakeholders, defining clear quality benchmarks at each project stage, and ensuring a uniform approach to data management.

2.4. Cost of non-quality

Ensuring quality has a cost. At the same time, there is also a cost of low quality (cost of non-quality or CONQ) [8]; it is therefore important to balance the costs associated with preventing quality issues against the costs incurred when mistakes/errors occur.

In a solution like AIDAVA data quality issues can have major consequences on patients' health, as the data managed in the systems would (when the system is in production) support care decisions for the patients by the treating physicians and deliver data for further clinical research. Non-quality of these data could therefore have a major impact, and the objective of AIDAVA is to maximise data quality while optimising the cost for ensuring this quality. This deliverable is therefore not further exploring the cost of non-quality and identifying the right balance between quality and non-quality. This should be envisioned as a research area.

2.5. Objectives of data quality in AIDAVA

2.5.1. Level 1: Collected data source

Assessing data quality at the primary source is of utmost importance, as it is the origin of the data. However, due to the design of AIDAVA, direct assessment at this stage is not in scope of the project. The engagement with the data holders is facilitated through a data transfer specification outlined in the data sharing agreement (see Deliverable D1.4. Definition of Assessment study). This implies that the data AIDAVA receives is subject to extraction - with potential transformation - processes before transfer. While our preference is for collecting raw data, it is important to recognize that the data received may not always be a complete representation of the original raw data. This discrepancy often arises due to potential intellectual property considerations and constraints from the electronic health record (EHR) systems, preventing the full disclosure of the entire dataset. Nevertheless, efforts need to be made to collaborate with the source data holders to understand the quality measure they employ and leverage any available metadata or documentation that sheds light on the data's reliability and integrity.

Level 1: Data store-raw data (source format)	
Data quality	At this level, data is being transferred from the original data source per Data Transfer

Level 1: Data store-raw data (source format)			
objective	<p>Specification (DTS). The only check that can be performed relates to consistency of the transferred data against the DTS.</p> <p>Note: It is worth considering the possibility of conducting a baseline data quality assessment for each data source, as this could provide valuable insights. Such an assessment would offer a more comprehensive understanding of data quality across the data life cycle. Additionally, it could prove instrumental in addressing the “fit for purpose” question, particularly from a secondary perspective. While this may be considered a “nice-to-have” item, it holds the potential to enhance the depth of our data quality evaluation.</p>		
Case of non-quality	Request to correct transferred data and resend. Do not proceed with curation of the data source to level 2.		
Data quality requirement related to level 1	Consistency	Assess data consistency against Data Transfer Specification (equivalent to the data dictionary).	Yes - No
	Completeness	Completeness of metadata defined in the Data Transfer Specification.	-

2.5.2. Level 2 and 3: Curated data (following data transformation into RDF format)

AIDAVA will mainly give attention to assessing the data curation and transformation process between the collected data sources and derived data. The transformation process is taking place in 2 steps:

1. Transformation and curation of one single collected data source-into a source knowledge graph (SKG)
2. Integration of the SKG with all the other already curated collected data sources, and addition of curation/ data quality enhancement process to deliver the full personal health knowledge graph (PHKG) which represents the personal longitudinal health record of the patient.

Data quality should be assessed at these two different levels.

Level 2: Data store-staging (SKG)			
Data quality objective	<p>At this level, data from a single data source have been transformed - and curated - into the required standard structure, the reference ontology, to deliver a source knowledge graph (SKG). The goal of an assessment is to ensure that the resulting SKG is of the appropriate quality level before it is integrated within the overall PHKG. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The curation of a text document through the NLP curation tool, can generate a lot of noise and should not be integrated into the PHKG before further curation. • A data source will not be integrated if all human interventions remain unanswered. 		
Case of non-quality	Do not integrate in the PHKG		
Data quality requirement	Consistency	All data in the SKG are assessed against the reference ontology (by type, by range, and by multivariable)	Threshold: 50%

Level 2: Data store-staging (SKG)			
related to level 2	Completeness	All data from level 1 are transformed into the SKG.	Threshold: 75% Unstructured data: Yes - No

Level 3: Data store curated (PHKG)			
Data quality objective	At this level, data from multiple sources have been integrated - and further curated - into the PHKG (containing all integrated SHKGs). The goal of an assessment is to ensure that the resulting PHKG is representative of the patient's medical record, and that it is fully compliant with the FAIR principles (on data and metadata level)		
Case of non-quality	Do not proceed to level 4.		
Data quality requirement related to level 3	Consistency	All data in the PHKG are assessed against the reference ontology (by type, by range, and by multivariable).	Threshold: 50%
	Completeness	All data from each SHKG are integrated in the PHKG.	Threshold: 75%

2.5.3. Level 4: derived data (following published process)

An assessment is needed to determine the level quality of the data published into the target format from the PHKG, for reuse (Level 4). At this level, the goal of the assessment is to evaluate and compare the level of quality with specific requirements defined by the data user. There can be many different formats published from the same PHKG - or set of PHKGs - for different purposes.

To ensure the data's fitness for purpose in the context of reuse, the Data Quality Labels and metadata will be matched with the specific requirements of the data user. By comparing the data user's quality expectations with the provided data quality overview, AIDAVA can assess whether the data meets the desired level of quality for their intended application.

It is essential to recognize that this process may differ for each reuse use case and might evolve over time. As new data requirements emerge or as the reuser's needs change, AIDAVA will adapt the data quality evaluation accordingly to continuously provide relevant and reliable data.

Level 4: Data store-published data (target format)	
Data quality objective	At this level, data from one or multiple PHKGs have been transformed into a target format required by the data user. The goal is to assess the quality of the data for that specific purpose. In AIDAVA, there are 3 different target outputs for 3 different purposes. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Generation of the Breast Cancer Registry extract - from multiple patient PHKGs - that supports federated data queries across 3 sites to demonstrate feasibility of a federated EU clinical registry across hospitals.

Level 4: Data store-published data (target format)			
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Computation of a CVD SMART label based on specific variable from a single PHKG, demonstrating that the PHKG can be used for supporting treating physician in clinical practices (not needed to compute the SMART label manually) 3. Generation of IPS in the required format - with any further work (Note: the completeness of the IPS will be directly related to the amount of collected data sources provided to the AIDAVA system) 		
Case of non-quality	Secondary use of data, not possible if the data is not fit for purpose		
Data quality requirement related to level 4	Consistency	All data transformed into the request format are assessed towards the secondary use case requirements.	Threshold: To be defined by a secondary user.
	Completeness	All data transformed will be assessed towards completeness based on the secondary use case requirements.	Threshold: To be defined by a secondary user.

3. Results

3.1. Metadata

Several categories of metadata were differentiated earlier in this document.

- Metadata on data source:
 - Care context metadata
 - Creation metadata
 - Data representation metadata
- Metadata on transformation steps
 - Computer traceability metadata
 - Curator traceability metadata
- Metadata on published output, at single patient level or for population dataset)
 - Generation metadata
 - Technical metadata
 - FAIR metadata (only for population datasets)

This section explains each of these categories and presents the information properties that each category should contain, along with its representation (data structure and semantics). It also explains the origin of this metadata and where they will be stored within AIDAVA for further use at the different levels of the data life cycle introduced before (see Section 2.3.1). Formal specifications for implementation of the metadata are provided in Annex 1.

The table below provides an overview of the management of this metadata in AIDAVA.

- Metadata related to data sources are expected to be included in the Data Transfer Specification (DTS), provided by each site as part of the Data Sharing Agreement. For situations in which mandatory metadata properties are not available and are needed as part of the workflow, the information will be required during the curation workflow. This metadata will be stored in the AIDAVA Catalogue of data sources; they will be enriched by mapping information as part of the Data Source Onboarding process.
- In terms of metadata related to transformation steps, i.e. the metadata related to each Source Knowledge Graph (SKG) and to the Personal Health Knowledge Graph (PHKG), they will be generated by the AIDAVA virtual assistant while processing the data and stored in the audit trail. This information, together with source related metadata inherited from the source data, will be also stored with each data item respectively in the SHKG and PHKG to support answers related to data lineage (i.e. information on where a specific data item has come from).
- Metadata related to published outputs will also be generated by the AIDAVA Virtual Assistant while processing the data and stored in the audit trail. Technical metadata related to technical format of the generated output might be appropriate - specifically in case of proprietary format and/or population data sets. In addition, in the case of population data sets, the AIDAVA Virtual Assistant will also generate FAIR metadata related to the content of the data set.

Metadata	Origin and storage of metadata	Data Source metadata			Transformation metadata		Published output metadata		
		Care	Creation	Technical	Computer traceability	Curator traceability	Generation	FAIR	Technical
Relevant Standard		NA	ISO 13606-1	DSV SQL RML	W3 Provenance (Schema.org, Bioschemas)		W3 Provenance	W3 DCAT	
LEVEL 1 (Source data)	<u>Origin</u> : DTS + manual update + Data Source Onboarding <u>Storage</u> : Data source catalogue	NA	YES	YES	-	-	-	-	-
LEVEL 2 SHKG	<u>Origin</u> : ingestion and curation workflows	NA	Inherited		Workflow execution		-	-	-
LEVEL 3 PHKG	<u>Storage</u> : audit-trail and SHKG/ PHKG	NA	Inherited		Inherited + Workflow execution		-	-	-
LEVEL 4 Published data	<u>Origin</u> : publishing workflow <u>Storage</u> : audit-trail and published output	NA	Inherited		Inherited + Workflow execution		Audit-trail	Not for single patient output (IPS, CVD label) Hardcoded for population data set (BC registry)	From specification of target output

Table 1. Overview of metadata across the AIDAVA data life cycle

3.1.1. Metadata on data source

Care context metadata

Individual electronic health record data items, such as a symptom, an examination finding, a test result, a prescription, originate within a care situation which confers an important interpretation context on the data. This is especially important to clinicians when looking back over historical record entries, but may also influence the reliable interpretation of data items for analysis.

The care context could include the location within a healthcare provider organisation that a clinical encounter took place (the emergency department, the ambulatory clinic, a ward, and intensive care unit etc.), and the situation that triggered the clinical encounter (an emergency event, a planned clinic visit, a routine follow-up, a screening invitation etc.). These contexts may influence the interpretation of individual data values, for example a blood pressure reading taken in the emergency department after a patient has collapsed should not be co-interpreted alongside that person's blood pressures being routinely monitored as part of hypertension management, as it will not reflect their steady state. A decision to prescribe an antibiotic for pneumonia might be taken more readily in an intensive care unit than in a clinic setting, complicating any study into appropriate and inappropriate antibiotic prescribing practices.

There is no standard that defines what information properties should be considered for inclusion as part of capturing this care context, although commonly cited properties include the precise care setting within a healthcare provider unit and the triggering situation for a clinical encounter (which ICPC calls "Reason for encounter"). In AIDAVA, specific context that enables the correct clinical interpretation of health data items will be extracted as additional data items, for example if a blood glucose test was performed while the patient was fasting, and not regarded as a separate kind of metadata.

Source level Creation metadata

This category of metadata describes the source at generic schema/system level: it specifies the legal entity that has provided the collected data, and the information system under the control of that entity from which the collected data has been exported.

The legal entity needs to be identified, possibly along with a legal or data protection contact, in case communication with that person is required.

Many healthcare providers e.g. hospitals have multiple internal information systems. If there is an advanced EHR then all the patient level data is probably concentrated into this one system, which is the single source system for all categories of data being exported for AIDAVA use. However, hospitals often have multiple deployed ICT products such as radiology systems, lab systems, pharmacy systems, intensive care systems, sometimes clinical speciality systems such as an endoscopy or echocardiogram system. AIDAVA needs to know the data source system for each category of data it receives, because this will dictate the form in which the data is exported and allows AIDAVA to keep a record of which ETL processes have been used for each providing system.

Annex 1 details the information properties needed for this source level creation metadata.

Patient level Creation metadata

A huge body of research on electronic health records, over the past 30 years, has highlighted the importance of information properties that specify the information relating to the context in which health data items were originally created and subsequently managed within an electronic health record system. The areas of creation context are well described in standards such as ISO 18308:2011 (Requirements for an electronic health record architecture). Creation metadata may be used within the AIDAVA workflow to verify that different information items are related to the same patient, to differentiate a patient from other information subjects if applicable, for example if processing family history information, and to utilise the real-world occurrence time of data entries for reasoning and inferences that could be used to enhance the record.

All the creation metadata that is possible to extract from an EHR should be retained within the AIDAVA PHKG, for clinicians and patients to trust the downstream data coming from AIDAVA for future care decisions.

AIDAVA has carefully examined the comprehensive inventory of requirements published in ISO 18308 and determined that the following information properties are of greatest relevance to extract from data sources, and likely to be available from the data sources.

- The person who is the subject of care: the subject of the EHR entry.
- The person who is the subject of information for an entry if it is not the subject of care.
- The identity of users who author or authorise entries in a health record (i.e. who have determined the information to be entered into an EHR).
- The date and time at which each health record entry was originally committed to the EHR repository.
- The care setting, organisation, and physical location at which a recorded healthcare activity has occurred.

Although not specifically part of the ISO 18308 requirements, it is also important to specify the type of clinical document that provides important context for interpreting the data, for example that a drug is specified in a prescription as opposed to an allergy list. A detailed description of these metadata is provided in Annex 1. They will be included in the files containing patient data, extracted from the local sources, and ingested into AIDAVA.

Technical representation metadata

Data representation metadata refers to detailed information about the technical aspects and characteristics of data within a system, enabling efficient management, understanding, and utilisation of the information. In the context of AIDAVA, to fulfil the requirement of automation in the curation process as well as explainability.

We identified 3 types of representation metadata.

- Metadata at the source level, providing information on extraction from the source system and exchange media; they must be included in the Data Transfer Specification (DTS), including the detailed technical specification of each data source to be transferred from a data holder to AIDAVA.
- Metadata at the level of data elements/attributes contained within the source, with individual patient data; they must be included in the Data Transfer Specification.

- Metadata at the level of data elements/attributes related to the mapping with the AIDAVA reference ontology; they will be included in the DTS as part of the Data Source Onboarding process (see *Deliverable D2.2. on the curation process*)

The list of technical representation metadata to be retained in AIDAVA is provided in Annex 1. This information will be provided by the different sites through the Data Transfer Specification and updated with mapping information during the Data Source Onboarding process; it will be stored in the Catalogue of Data Source (Deliverable D3.3)

3.1.2. Metadata on transformation

To represent that transformation metadata, we followed the principles of the W3 Provenance data-model³ with the following mapping.

- Entity: attribute within the data source or concept within a knowledge graph.
- Activity: a workflow with different steps to support the transformations. Each steps includes a startTime and an endTime.
- Agent: a software responsible for the transformation of data (e.g. NLP, AI coding, ETL...), or a data quality checks (SHACL rule) or a person in case of manual intervention

Computer traceability metadata

AIDAVA is pioneering a set of data transformation processes - through a set of well-defined workflows see *Deliverable No. 2.2 Details on data curation & publishing process* - that are anticipated to enhance the computable value of the health data currently held in EHR systems. It is implementing a pipeline that starts with EHR data extraction and mapping to a semantic representation as a knowledge graph, called Data Source Onboarding, and then calls different (AI based) tools based on the interoperability issue to be solved. For instance, the NLP curation tool may parse narrative texts such as clinic letters and discharge reports, and map concepts found in those to clinical terms that supplement the structured and coded EHR data extract. AI based coding tools may identify appropriate code data that can be inferred from the existing narrative data. It is assumed that these processes will not modify the imported source data but provide a different representation in the form of a personal health knowledge graph (The curation role of patients and caregivers is discussed in the next section).

Each of these transformations is subject to change – improvement – because of learning during the piloting phase. The pipeline therefore needs to document when and how each transformation was

³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>

undertaken on records, including the version-specific rules, software, execution engines and validations used for each transformation.

The AIDAVA enhanced patient record will therefore contain some (useful) data items that were not in the original EHR but have been added by AIDAVA. For downstream users of the data, whether for patient care or analytics, it will be important that the basis on which each data item is present is clear, which means the AIDAVA added data must be clearly labelled as such.

It is therefore important that AIDAVA creates and curates' traceability metadata precisely specifying the transformations to the source data that have been applied through its pipeline:

- the mapping rules to transform the source EHR data into the PHKG.
- the workflow and related transformation tools (curation tool and Data Quality Checks) that were used when performing the transformation of data source into the patient knowledge graph, the version of the transformation tools, any method adopted for handling inconsistencies within the data because of these transformations (e.g. identifying and resolving conflicting diagnosis)
- when and on what time stamped each transformation was performed

Human Curator traceability metadata

The final step in the AIDAVA enhancement pipeline is a human one. Each patient or their nominated caregiver (or exceptionally, a health or care professional nominated by the patient) will support the VA when automation is not possible during the correction workflow and as part of different targeted quality checks on completeness, correctness, semantic inconsistencies... as described before. This may result in changes being proposed by the curator to AIDAVA generated data (e.g. to disagree with an inferred diagnosis). The curator might also create new data items that they feel are missing (e.g. to add a former diagnosis, or an important over the counter medication).

For both healthcare and analytics data re-users and for AIDAVA to learn, it will be important that each data item that is added or revised by a patient or a curator is clearly labelled as such. The provenance metadata set described earlier in this chapter could be reused here, specifying who the curator is and when their changes were made. It may also be appropriate to cater for comments to be put in by the curator as annotation remarks on the data (e.g. to express uncertainty, to explain a change)

3.1.3. Metadata on derived (published) output

One of the important principles and benefits of AIDAVA is that the computer-enriched and curator-enriched Personal Health Knowledge Graph is the single source of the most complete truth regarding the health information about each patient. It is the definitive source from which enhanced EHR extracts can be offered back to the clinical coalface, to view or even to re-import back into the healthcare provider system. It is the same definitive source from which data sets specific to analysis use cases and user requests can be generated, repeatedly and consistently, so that these generated data sets do not need to be separately stored by AIDAVA or by the end user.

AIDAVA is strongly committed to following the FAIR principles regarding how it makes data sets discoverable and available to downstream users. To be able to repeatedly re-generate an identical dataset, it will be necessary to store a set of metadata to support the FAIR principles and ensure that

the published output is not only discoverable and available to downstream users but are also interoperable and reusable. This includes the following.

FAIR level	Needed metadata
Findable	Data generation metadata with information allowing to map research criteria with the published output. Since datasets may sometimes be generated on demand, the Findable metadata will need to be produced and published for data sets that <u>can</u> be generated, not only those that have been generated.
Accessible	Data access metadata. In the AIDAVA context this may need to be elaborated to include a data set generation request specification, i.e. not only how to access a data set that exists but how to request that a particular data set be generated.
Interoperable	Specification of the target format, including the use of specified standards. Since AIDAVA will often generate data sets according to a user's needs, derived from its PHKG source of truth, the Interoperable metadata might at times be a list of options for standards that AIDAVA can output to.
Reusable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer and curator traceability metadata - with information on the transformation (ensuring there is a data lineage on the data, for liability purpose) • Data generation metadata

Data set generation metadata

This needs to include:

- an identifier of the data set that has been generated
- the characteristics of the patients that were included (for example, patients with a particular disease severity, from a given country, within a particular age range)
- the inventory of data items included, out of the overall PHKG inventory
- whether the dataset covers all the data sources or was deliberately limited to ones (for example, only Estonian hospitals)
- whether the dataset was specified to include only original source EHR data, also the computer enhanced data, also the curator enhanced data etc.
- the version state (timestamp) of the PHKG from which the data set was generated, as well as the date and time when it was generated; this property is required to regenerate the same data content in the future that was generated on a past occasion, rather than an updated version, and requires PHKG rollback capability.

This list of generation metadata is particularly important because AIDAVA intends to generate at least some data sets on demand. This means that the requester needs to specify the data they wish to have access to, and the data set needs to confirm what patient and data extraction characteristics (e.g. what selection criteria) were used for its generation.

The metadata related to data set publication, implementing the FAIR principles and with relevant additional properties, will be represented using the standard that is intended for adoption by the European Health Data Space. This will be a health specific profile of the D-CAT metadata catalogue standard, which is presently being developed and validated by the HealthData@EU pilot. A preliminary version of their catalogue proposal has been published⁴. AIDAVA will track the finalisation

⁴ http://search.healthdataportal.eu/sandbox/listDCAT_tables_provenance.py

of this, map to it and publish data set availability using it. This AIDAVA mapping will be added as requirements in *Deliverable 1.9 for inclusion in G2* - also with requirements related to the visualisation of this metadata.

The description set for the patient characteristics is likely to be relatively simple and can draw on the patient profile and characteristics that are often used to describe data sets within a data catalogue, or to define patients who are eligible for a clinical trial. It would seem logical for AIDAVA to reuse such patterns rather than invent another one. The description set for the inventory of data items will inevitably match the data item content of the PHKG. The other metadata aspects mentioned above should have descriptors identified in the DCAT standard in accordance with the EHDS2 pilot data catalogue for secondary dataset; the list of attributes to be used from the DCAT-AP standard is provided in Annex 1.

It will sometimes be necessary to re-generate an identical dataset multiple times because a particular time point of the PHKG content is itself valuable for data uses (e.g. what was the evidence available at the time when a decision was taken). However, it is more likely that a dataset corresponding to inclusion criteria will be re-generated from time to time, containing more up-to-date information on existing patients and possibly additional patients who have been added since the last time of generation. It is therefore important that the metadata regarding dataset generation also captures and preserves information about the version history of data sets if the precise inclusion criteria are reapplied at multiple time points to refresh a dataset with newer or more complete data than was previously available.

All this metadata, relating to data sets rather than to fine-grained patient level data, will not belong in the knowledge graph but need to be represented and stored within a separate repository developed for this specific purpose.

It should be noted that the ability for a user to make use of incrementally updated dataset may require the use of pseudonym identifiers. The positioning of pseudonymised data within the AIDAVA landscape is the subject of Task 4.1.

Data set access metadata

AIDAVA will at times act as a data provider, making data sets available to third parties for a diversity of purposes. It will need to be accountable for the ways in which it determines the suitability of organisations to receive and use (or to remotely query) AIDAVA curated data. Below the level of organisations, it will need to have approval criteria for each dataset or data access request from each approved organisation, a process for receiving and evaluating each request, a robust documentation process for how each request has been handled and an audit trail of dataset generation and provision or remote access.

Some of this material might be appropriate to publish (e.g. on our website) for transparency to the public.

The definition of what dataset needs to be kept about data access requests, their evaluation and the decision-making process, and the granting of data access, will be the subject of future work in Task 4.1, and is not elaborated further in this deliverable.

3.2. Data Quality Checks

3.2.1. Data Quality Check categorization

Data Quality Checks are instrumental in securing high quality data. Rules-based data quality assessment has been used by prior research to detect data quality errors [9]. In addition to leveraging established Data Quality Checks from academic literature, our approach within AIDAVA includes a comprehensive exploration of both white and grey literature to identify a broader spectrum of Data Quality Checks. White literature is the formally published works, and grey literature includes reports, theses, and other non-commercial forms of publication. A search for Data Quality Checks has been initiated and current findings are captured in Annex 2. An important next step is to further scan grey and white literature for relevant Data Quality Checks. This will ensure that we have a wide collection of Data Quality Checks suitable for AIDAVA and specific towards both use cases – namely, cardiovascular disease and breast cancer.

Once these Data Quality Checks have been compiled, we proceed to systematically map them against a standardised template. This template is designed to categorise and organise the rules effectively, allowing for a structured assessment of data quality across various dimensions. The template will also facilitate the adaptation and integration of these rules into our data quality assessment framework, ensuring consistency and comprehensiveness in our evaluation process.

Categorization of Data Quality Checks	Description	Example
Dimension	This represents the broad category of data quality, encompassing a general area of focus within which specific data quality issues can be identified and addressed.	<i>Consistency</i>
Subdimension	This represents a further level of granularity. Subdimensions break down the broader category into more detailed areas of concern, allowing for a more nuanced assessment of data quality.	<i>Relational</i>
Category	This represents the most specific category within the data quality hierarchy and pertains to attributes or elements of the data where quality rules can be applied.	<i>Gender and diagnoses</i>
Class	This represents the variable for which a Data Quality Check has been established.	<i>Mal neo breast central (ICD10 C50.119)</i>
<i>Data Quality Check</i>	This represents the actionable requirements that are applied to the data class to assess and ensure its quality.	<i>Patients diagnosed with C50.119 should be identified as female in their medical records.</i>

The following table provides detailed information on each dimension, subdimension, and category derived from our literature review.

Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Description
Consistency	Value	Data type	Ensure that the unit of each value are correct and consistent.

Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Description
	Out of range	Lab value	Lab values should fall within acceptable ranges.
		Observation value	Observation values should fall within acceptable ranges.
	Relational	Date and time error	Dates and times should be consistent with the sequence of clinical events.
		Age and procedure	The patient's age should be appropriate for the specified procedures.
		Gender and diagnosis	Certain diagnoses should correspond to the patient's gender, though rare exceptions exist.
		Common sense	Data entries should be logically consistent.
	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results
Diagnosis and lab results			Diagnoses should be supported by corresponding lab results, confirming the clinical picture.
Common sense			All critical fields should be populated in a way that makes sense within the context of the patient's overall health record.
Value		Common sense	All critical fields should be populated in a way that makes sense within the context of the patient's overall health record.

This table presents the most current overview of data quality dimensions, subdimensions, and categories as per latest comprehensive review of relevant literature. Please note that the contents may evolve beyond this deliverable as we continue to scan the literature for additional Data Quality Checks.

Annex 3 provides an overview of selected Data Quality Checks extracted from existing sources.

3.2.2. Governance of Data Quality Checks

In ensuring the integrity and utility of our data, we recognize the pivotal role of robust governance in the selection, application, and maintenance of Data Quality Checks. This chapter outlines the structured approach we will adapt to govern the lifecycle of these rules, from sourcing to periodic updates.

Establishing source relevance criteria

The following table serves as our governance framework for evaluating and selecting sources that will provide us with these Data Quality Checks. By following these criteria, we ensure our data quality framework containing existing Data Quality Checks is built on validated, state-of-the-art methodologies.

Title	Title of the document.

Author	The names and credentials of the individuals or organisations who authored the content. Experts in healthcare data management or similar fields are preferable.
Credibility	The trustworthiness of the source, based on the authors' expertise, the reputation of the publishing body, and the source's track record in the field of healthcare data.
Validation and research	The extent to which the content is supported by scientific research, case studies, or empirical data. It should be based on tested methods or widely accepted practices in healthcare data management.
Currency	The timeliness of the information, considering the rapid evolution of both healthcare and data technology. The content should reflect the most recent standards and practices.
Dimensional relevance	The relevance of the content to various dimensions of data quality such as completeness, consistency, timeliness, correctness... In a first phase, we will mainly focus on completeness and consistency, but content related to other dimensions will be stored for future relevance.
Content relevance	The degree to which the content specifically addresses the use cases defined within AIDAVA. Data Quality Checks related to other disease areas will be stored for future relevance.
Copyright and licensing	The legal permissions for use, indicating whether the content is freely available, under a specific licence, or has usage restrictions that might affect its reuse.
Technical compatibility	The compatibility of the content with the data systems and technologies within AIDAVA. This includes formats, standards, and interoperability considerations.
Ease of adaptation	How easily the content can be adapted or integrated into processes and systems defined in AIDAVA. This includes considerations of format, complexity, and the need for customization.

Extraction of Data Quality Checks

Upon the successful identification of sources that meet our defined relevance criteria, we initiate the extraction of Data Quality Checks. This process is presently being done manually to ensure nuanced understanding and contextual alignment. In the immediate term, this manual approach affords us the precision necessary to extract Data Quality Checks to our use cases' unique demands. Each rule is documented with its source and context to maintain a clear and traceable lineage of information. This ensures not only transparency but also the ability to revisit and comprehend the rationale behind each rule's extraction.

Annex 3 provides an overview of selected Data Quality Check sources.

Rule validation and integration

Validation is crucial to our process. Each extracted rule will undergo testing to confirm its effectiveness. Upon successful validation, rules will be carefully integrated into our current system, with attention to compatibility and complementarity with existing rules.

Updating and evolving the rule set: Maintenance and periodic review

In a landscape where data evolves rapidly, our rule set must be equally dynamic. We will establish processes to monitor and incorporate advancements in data management practices, emerging data types, and technological breakthroughs. Collaborating with a broader community of data quality practitioners, we will stay informed of the latest trends and integrate these learnings into our rule set, thus maintaining its relevance and effectiveness.

3.2.3. Rule format & Link with the ontology

The format of the rules and their linkage with the ontology are comprehensively detailed in sections 3.3.3 and 3.3.4 of deliverable 2.1 [3]. For an in-depth understanding and continuity of context, we refer to these sections within the mentioned document.

3.2.4. Running rules: data quality engine

We plan to use the Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) for data quality assessment. SHACL, an acronym for "Shapes Constraint Language," is a specification designed to validate Resource Description Framework (RDF) graphs. SHACL Engines serve as powerful tools for checking the integrity of personal knowledge graphs against predefined rules or shapes. A SHACL engine would validate a source RDF knowledge graph against a set of constraints defined in Shapes graph and output a SHACL Validation Report as the result of the validation process.

Through SHACL validation, users can obtain reports detailing the conformance of their graphs against SHACL shapes. However, it is worth noting that SHACL engines primarily focus on identifying the presence of violations rather than providing elaborate explanations about these violations. A typical validation report may provide guidance on how to identify or fix violation, but often lacks clarity for humans to pinpoint the root cause of an error, providing generic messages. For instance, the example report may state, "Admission date must be before discharge date," without displaying specific details about the admission and discharge dates, making it challenging for users to understand the exact issue.

To be able to provide more contextual messages for users to resolve violations, we integrated custom messages into shapes to facilitate the retrieval of additional information about violations. We developed a SHACL report parser to extract details from the report and enrich the message with context from the source knowledge graph. This context information could include admission and discharge dates and the source of this knowledge.

3.3. Data Quality Labels

3.3.1. Objective

The Data Quality Labels at AIDAVA serves as a transparent indicator of the data we collect from the source and the enhancements it undergoes within our processing pipeline. The scoring system is developed to measure and demonstrate these improvements quantitatively, providing all stakeholders a clear visual representation of the added value AIDAVA contributes through its data management practices.

The quality label will be computed for the current situation (G0) whenever relevant, for the first generation of the prototype (G1, targeted for July 2024) and for the second generation of the prototype (G2, targeted for March 2026); they will be used as primary endpoint (Metric #3) defined in Deliverable D1.4 Assessment Study Protocol [2] and will support the statistical analysis to assess the overall performance of the AIDAVA prototype.

3.3.2. Data Quality Labels computation for Level 2 and Level 3

The computation of the Data Quality Labels is an important step in evaluating the quality of the data from different sources (SHKG, Level 2) and the integrated patient record (PHKG, Level 3). This process is designed to reflect a comprehensive view of the data’s adherence to quality standards through a transparent, pass or fail approach for each rule. Here is how we perform the label computation.

Pass/Fail approach	Each rule within our dataset is subjected to a binary assessment – it either passes or fails. A pass indicates that the data meets the specific criteria set out by the rule, while a failure denotes a deviation from the expected standard. This binary approach simplifies the evaluation process, allowing for a straightforward calculation of quality labels.
Category label	For every category, which might consist of diverse rules, we calculate the

	percentage of rules that have passed. This involves tallying the number of passes and dividing by the total number of rules within that category, converting it into a percentage. This percentage represents the label for the category and is a direct indicator of how well the data complies with the rules defined for that specific aspect of the dataset.
Subdimension label	Broader subdimensions that encapsulate related categories, undergo a similar scoring process. We aggregate the pass rates of all the underlying rules in a category to find its average label. This label can be considered a quantitative measure that showcases the data’s conformity to our quality standards at a more granular level, accounting for the nuances and specificities of different levels.
Dimension label	The dimension label is a comprehensive metric that reflects the aggregated performance across multiple subdimensions, providing a high-level view of adherence to the established quality criteria within a broader aspect of the dataset.
Weighted averages	In the scoring aggregation, it is essential to account for the varying number of checks within each level and category. Since not all levels or categories contain an equal number of rules, a weighted average approach is employed to ensure that each section of the dataset contributes proportionately to the final label.

3.3.3. Data Quality Labels computation for Level 4

3.3.4 Data Quality Labels visualisation

Visualising the Data Quality Labels is a critical aspect of our project that requires careful consideration and planning. In the current phase, our primary focus has been on integrating existing Data Quality Checks and developing a robust maintenance framework for these rules. Due to time constraints, an in-depth exploration of the visualisation process has been possible within this deliverable’s time frame. We acknowledge the significance of this step and are committed to addressing the visualisation of Data Quality Labels as a priority in our subsequent efforts.

4. Next steps and conclusions

4.1. Next steps to be complete for G2

4.1.1. Implementation of metadata

The metadata described above are being implemented through different mechanisms specified in the table below.

Metadata	Implementation mechanism
Creation metadata	AIDAVA ingestion workflow (Deliverable 3.6 - G1 prototype and Deliverable 3.10 - G2 prototype)
Technical representation metadata	Data Source Catalogue (Deliverable D3.3)
Transformation metadata	AIDAVA curation workflow (Deliverable 3.6 - G1 prototype and Deliverable 3.10 - G2 prototype)
Published output metadata	AIDAVA publishing workflow (Deliverable 3.6 - G1 prototype and Deliverable 3.10 - G2 prototype)

4.1.2. Visualisation of Data Quality Labels

Developing a visualisation for the Data Quality Labels is on our roadmap as a subsequent action post this deliverable. Effective visualisation is key to understanding and communicating the quality of data briefly and will be prioritised in the next phase of the project.

4.2. More research around DQ framework (out of the scope of AIDAVA)

4.2.1. Towards Data Quality Checks - Data Quality Check version management

We have developed a governance framework and a categorization system for Data Quality Checks . This system is designed to efficiently manage and apply these rules across different datasets within the project. The next step involves conducting a thorough literature review to explore and gather existing Data Quality Checks. This step is vital for enhancing our data quality framework by incorporating a broad range of validated rules in AIDAVA. While our immediate focus is on applying these Data Quality Checks to two specific use cases – breast cancer and cardiovascular disease areas – we recognize the potential benefits of broadening our scope. Gathering Data Quality Checks that emphasise other disease areas is also crucial, as the project intends to reuse health data from various pathologies. This inclusive approach ensures that AIDAVA remains adaptable and relevant to a wide range of health data applications.

4.2.2. Towards a data quality and utility label for HealthData@EU

In our pursuit of enhancing the quality and utility of health data within AIDAVA, we are exploring the opportunity to collaborate with the QUANTUM project. QUANTUMs objective is to develop a label mechanism designed to certify the quality and utility of datasets. The essence of this collaboration lies in adopting and integrating a label that not only attests to the data's quality and utility but also reflects the data providers' maturity level in managing and assuring data quality.

4.3 Recommendation for the EHDS

Based on the work done in this deliverable, we suggest extending the recommendations on data quality from the TEHDAS project in Deliverable D6.3 [11] with the following ones.

1. Data quality measurement should be enforced as soon as possible - and affordable - in the data life cycle. Whenever possible, it should be done at data sources. If not, possible it should be done on the curated data sources, expected to be available into an interoperable and reusable format; in the case of AIDAVA this is the Personal Health Knowledge Graph, an RDF format constrained by the AIDAVA ontology.
2. Data quality measurement instruments should be adapted to each data life cycle (data sources, curated data, published data) as each cycle has a different purpose.
3. Metadata proposed for inclusion in the catalogue of secondary datasets set being developed in EHDS2 pilot with health DCAT-AP, should also be considered for describing collected data, at the source.
4. A catalogue of datasets - be it collected data or derived data - should include technical representation metadata as described in this document to ensure smooth reuse

Annexes

Annex 1. Detailed description of Metadata

Source level Creation Metadata

Field	Optionality	Data Type	Description
SCHEMA LEVEL			
uniqueSourceID	Mandatory	II (instance identifier)	A unique identifier of the resource (i.e. table) being described or catalogued.
sourceName	Mandatory	string	A human readable version of the name given to the resource; it is needed to support explanations to the patient
table	Mandatory	string	Table or object included in the source (as specified in the DTS tab sheet)
sourceType	Optional	string	Type of the data source (e.g. lab report, discharge summary, pathology report...) Note: As there is no formal standard value set for this attribute, it was decided to allow free text.
description	Optional	string	A free-text account of the resource.
mediaType	Mandatory	CV (coded value)	The media type of the distribution as defined by IANA [IANA-MEDIA-TYPES] [12].
createdBy	Mandatory	string	Name of the organisation issuing the DTS
creationDate	Mandatory	time	Date of the creation of the DTS (and time of import in the Catalogue of Data Sources)
responsibleDataStewards	Mandatory	II (instance identifier)	Person who can answer question on the data source and who can be contacted in case of issue Note: in the DTS this information will be provided as a string. This can be replaced by the identified when the master data of the different stakeholders of AIDAVA is in place
language	Optional	CV (coded value)	A language of the resource. This refers to the natural language used for the textual values in the data (Note: a data source may include different languages)

Patient Level Creation Metadata

The list below specifies the representation of these properties utilising the information model of ISO 13606-1:2019 (Electronic Health record Communication Part 1: Reference Model) - at the level of the COMPOSITION

Namespace	HL7 data type/ISO21090	Description	Optionality
ISO13606::	subject_of_care	II (instance identifier)	Mandatory
	subject_of_information_category	CV (coded value)	Optional
	composer	II (instance identifier)	Mandatory
		The primary person whose health and healthcare the EHR documents	
		The relationship category of person or object about whom the information in an entry relates to the subject of care	
		Healthcare actor responsible for creating, synthesising, or organising information that is committed to an EHR. The composer takes responsibility for its inclusion in that EHR, even if not the originator of it or the committer of it. =authorPerson in IHE ITI-TF3 (note: an author belongs to an institution and has a specialist).	

Namespace ISO13606::	HL7 data type/ ISO21090	Description	Optionality
			Note: for data privacy issues - sites have decided NOT to provide the real name of the composer (who may be a provider not involved and aware of AIDAVA) but will provide a generic name linked with the name of the service/department
committer data	- Optional	II (instance identifier)	Actor responsible for putting the health data into the EHR, which might be the logged in user typing in some dictated text, transcribing from a handwritten note, documenting on behalf of a colleague or a medical device automatically entering data into the EHR. Note: not all EHR systems distinguish the composer from the committer, and only identify one party, the logged in user of the EHR system who entered the data, in which case the property committee should be used = legalAuthenticator in IHE ITI-TF3 Note2: see above
auditEventTi mestamp	Optional	TS (timestamp)	The data and time at which an entry was committed to the EHR repository =creationTime in IHE ITI-TF3
authorSpecial ty	Optional	CV (coded value)	The specific specialty within a healthcare facility under which the human and/or machines authored the source 'document'. This attribute may be absent if not applicable.

Subject_of_information_category coded value

Code	Meaning	Description
DS00	subject of care	<i>healthcare actor</i> with a <i>person role</i> ; who seeks to receive, is receiving, or has received healthcare
DS01	relative of subject of care	<i>person role</i> being any human relative, without limitation to biological or adoptive relatives
DS02	next of kin	<i>person role</i> being either the closest living relative of the <i>subject of care</i> or identified as the one he has a close relationship with
DS03	foetus or neonate or infant	the baby or babies being described by an ENTRY in the EHR of the mother
DS04	mother	the mother of a foetus or neonate, if being described in the EHR of a baby (e.g. during pregnancy)
DS05	donor	<i>person role</i> being the donor of an organ or body specimen being described by an ENTRY in the EHR of the recipient
DS06	unrelated person	<i>person role</i> being any other person not related to the subject of care, such as an employer, friend, carer
DS07	healthcare third party	<i>healthcare actor</i> (organisation or person) other than a <i>healthcare provider</i> or the <i>subject of care</i>
DS08	subject of care proxy	<i>healthcare third party</i> having <i>person role</i> with the right to take decisions on behalf of the subject of care

The composer and committer-data identified in the table above belong to a healthcare organisation and service department that may be adopted by AIDAVA, as a subset of the following tables taken from ISO 13606-3 (see suggestions in blue font).

HealthcarePersonnel

Namespace ISO13606::	HL7 data type/ ISO21090	Description	Optionality	Value set
personID	II (instance identifier)			
personName		A name of the person	mandatory	
photo		A photo of this person	optional	
personIdentifier		A identifier of the person (hospital id, SSN, National id)		
address		An email address, telephone number and home or office addresses	optional	
active		This person's record is in active use		
birthDate		The date on which the person was born	optional	
civil status		Marital status	optional	
gender		The gender (male, female, unknown) of the person	optional	
language		The languages that healthcare personnel mastered	mandatory	
healthcareOrganization		The healthcare organisation that the healthcare personnel having a role in	mandatory	

HealthcareOrganisation

Namespace ISO13606::	HL7 data type/ ISO21090	Description	Optionality	Value set
healthcareOrganiza tionName		Name used for the organisation	mandatory	
name		A name of the healthcare organisation		
type		A type of name		
address		An email address, telephone number and/ or office addresses		
active		Whether the organisation's record is still in active use		
type		Kind of organisation		
healthcareOrganiza tionIdentifier		An identifier of the healthcare organisation		
contact		Contact for the organisation for a certain purpose		
contactId		Identifier for the contact		
purpose		The type of the contact		

ServiceDepartment

Namespace ISO13606::	HL7 data type/ ISO21090	Description	Optionality	Value set
serviceDepartment Name		A name of the service department	mandatory	
value		A textual representation of a name of the service department		
type		A type of the name		
serviceDepartment Address		An email address, telephone number and home or office addresses		
serviceDepartment Id		An identifier for service department		
value		A textual representation of a identifier of the service department		
type		A type of the identifier		
isPartOf		This service department is a part of the healthcare organisation or another service department		
contactId				
purpose				

Technical Representation Metadata

Field Name	Explanation	Required	Example
Source	Source of the Data	Yes	EHR
Table	Table or Object name	Yes	ENCOUNTER
HumanReadableName	Human Readable Name of the Field	Yes	Patient Name
VariableName	Variable Name as appears in the dataset	Yes	patient_name
IsPrimaryKey	Is the Variable a primary key	Yes	True or False
TableReference	If the Variable is a foreign key, the table name of the foreign key	No	PATIENT
VariableReference	If the Variable is a foreign key, the variable name of the foreign key	No	patient_id
IsMandatory	Is the Variable Mandatory	Yes	True or False
PrimitiveDataType	Primitive Type of the Variable. System checks if the data is in the correct type	Yes	string, int, float, bool
FHIRPrimitiveType	Fields primitive type according to the FHIR specifications	Yes	string, code, date etc.
ValueRestrictionType	Type or ValueSet for the Variable	No	NumberRange, DateRange, ValueSet, NA/Not applicable
ValueRestriction	Allowed Values for the Variable	No if ValueRestrictionType is None or Empty	10-20 or 01/01/2020-01/01/2021 or ValueSet URI
Description	Description of the Variable	No if the Variable is self explanatory	Patient Name
Example	Example of the Variable	No if the Variable is self explanatory	John Doe

Metadata on Transformation (and data lineage)

The ER diagram below provides a description of the transformation metadata that will be included in the data lineage within the AIDAVA prototype. It allows the capture transformation done by the computer (computer traceability metadata) or by the curator (human curator traceability metadata).

Annex 2. Overview of sources of Data Quality Check

Source Number	Title	Author	Credibility	Validation and research	Currency	Dimensional relevance	Content relevance	Copyright and licensing	Technical compatibility	Ease of adaptation
1	Rule-Based Data Quality Assessment and Monitoring System in Healthcare Facilities [13]	Wang et al.	Studies in Health Technology and Informatics	Academic paper	2019	Yes	Yes	Open source	Yes	Yes
2	Electronic health record data quality variability across a multistate clinical research network [14]	Mohamed et al.	Journal of Clinical and translational Science	Academic paper	2023	Yes	Yes	Open source	Yes	Yes
3	Representing rules for clinical data quality assessment based on OpenEHR guideline definition language [15]	Tian et al.	Studies in Health Technology and Informatics	Academic paper	2019	Yes	Yes	Open source	Yes	Yes
4	A proposal on cancer data quality checks: one common procedure [16]	Martos Jimenez M et al.	Cancer data quality checks working group	JRC publication	2014	Yes	Yes	Open source	Yes	Yes

Annex 3. Overview of selected Data Quality Checks

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Total cholesterol	Value should be collected in mg/dL
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	High -Density Lipoprotein (HDL)	Value should be collected in mg/dL
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL)	Value should be collected in mg/dL
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Troponin I (Tnl)	Value should be collected in mg/dL
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	C-Reactive Protein	Value should be collected in mg/L
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Triglycerides	Value should be collected in mg/dL
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Blood pressure systolic	Value should be collected in mmHg
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Blood pressure diastolic	Value should be collected in mmHg
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Weight	Value should be collected in kg
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Height	Value should be collected in meter
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	BMI	Value should be collected in kg/m ²
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Heart rate	Value should be collected in beats/min
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Albumin	Value should be collected in g/dL
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	Creatinine	Value should be collected in mg/dL
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	ALT	Value should be collected in IU/L
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	AST	Value should be collected in IU/L
1	Consistency	Value	Data type	GGT	Value should be collected in IU/L
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	Total cholesterol	Values should be within the range of 5,00 mg/dL to 200,00 mg/dL
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	High -Density Lipoprotein (HDL)	Values should be within the range of 5,00 mg/dL to 200,00 mg/dL
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL)	Values should be within the range of 0,00 mg/dL to 999,00 mg/dL
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	Troponin I (Tnl)	Values should be within the range of 0,03 ng/mL to 80,00 mg/dL
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	C-Reactive Protein	Values should be within the range of 5,00 mg/L to 600,00 mg/L
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	Triglycerides	Values should be within the range 10 mg/dL to 5000 mg/dL
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	Albumin	Values should be within the range of 1 g/dL to 14 g/dL
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	Creatinine	Values should be within the range of 0,1 mg/dL to 40 mg/dL

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	ALT	Values should be within the range of 5 IU/L to 26000 IU/L
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	AST	Values should be within the range of 5 IU/L to 26000 IU/L
1	Consistency	Out of range	Lab value	GGT	Values should be within the range of 5 IU/L to 30000 IU/L
1	Consistency	Out of range	Observation data elements	Age	Values should be within the range of 0 years to 140 years
1	Consistency	Out of range	Observation data elements	Blood pressure systolic	Values should be within the range of 20 mmHg to 350 mmHg
1	Consistency	Out of range	Observation data elements	Blood pressure diastolic	Values should be within the range of 20 mmHg to 350 mmHg
1	Consistency	Out of range	Observation data elements	Weight	Values should be within the range of 1 kg to 300 kg
1	Consistency	Out of range	Observation data elements	Height	Values should be within the range of 0,1 meter to 3 meter
3	Consistency	Out of range	Observation data elements	BMI	Values should be within the range of 5 to 70 kg/m ²
3	Consistency	Out of range	Observation data elements	Heart rate	Values should be within the range of 20 beats/min to 200 beats/min
1	Consistency	Relational	Age and procedure	CPT code 33822	If a patient is prescribed CPT code 33822 (Repair of patent ductus arteriosus), the age of the patient must be under 18 years.
1	Consistency	Relational	Age and procedure	CPT code 33824	If a patient is prescribed CPT code 33824 (Repair of patent ductus arteriosus), the age of the patient must be 18 years or older.
1	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Admit date	If the patient has an admit date, this should be after date of birth.
1	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Collection date	If the patient has a date when specimen was collected, this should be after date of birth.
1	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Last occurrence date	If the patient has a last occurrence date, this should be after date of birth.
3	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Medical history date	If the patient has a date when the medical history was collected, this should be after date of birth.
3	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Diagnosis date	If the patient has a diagnosis date, this should be after date of birth.
3	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Procedure date	If the patient has a procedure date, this should be after date of birth.
3	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Discharge date	If the patient has a discharge date, this should be after date of birth.
3	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Smoking date	If the patient has a smoking date, this should be after date of birth.
3	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Death date	If the patient has a dead date, this should be after date of birth.
3	Consistency	Relational	Date and time error	Discharge date	If the patient has a discharge date, this should be after admit date.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and	Scrotal varices (ICD10 I86.1)	Patients diagnosed with I86.1 should be identified as male in their medical records.

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
			diagnosis		
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Vulval varices (ICD10 I86.3)	Patients diagnosed with I86.3 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malig neo nipple (ICD10 C50.019)	Patients diagnosed with C50.019 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malig neo nipple (ICD10 C50.011)	Patients diagnosed with C50.011 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malig neo nipple (ICD10 C50.012)	Patients diagnosed with C50.012 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast-central (ICD10 C50.119)	Patients diagnosed with C50.119 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast-central (ICD10 C50.111)	Patients diagnosed with C50.111 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast-central (ICD10 C50.112)	Patients diagnosed with C50.112 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast up-inner (ICD10 C50.219)	Patients diagnosed with C50.219 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast up-inner (ICD10 C50.211)	Patients diagnosed with C50.211 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast up-inner (ICD10 C50.212)	Patients diagnosed with C50.212 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast low-inner (ICD10 C50.319)	Patients diagnosed with C50.319 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast low-inner (ICD10 C50.311)	Patients diagnosed with C50.311 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast low-inner (ICD10 C50.312)	Patients diagnosed with C50.312 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast up-outer (ICD10 C50.419)	Patients diagnosed with C50.419 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast up-outer (ICD10 C50.411)	Patients diagnosed with C50.411 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast up-outer (ICD10 C50.412)	Patients diagnosed with C50.412 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast low-outer (ICD10 C50.519)	Patients diagnosed with C50.519 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast low-outer (ICD10 C50.511)	Patients diagnosed with C50.511 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast low-outer (ICD10 C50.512)	Patients diagnosed with C50.512 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast-axillary (ICD10 C50.619)	Patients diagnosed with C50.619 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast-axillary (ICD10 C50.611)	Patients diagnosed with C50.611 should be identified as female in their medical records.

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo breast-axillary (ICD10 C50.612)	Patients diagnosed with C50.612 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malign neopl breast NEC (ICD10 C50.819)	Patients diagnosed with C50.819 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malign neopl breast NEC (ICD10 C50.811)	Patients diagnosed with C50.811 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malign neopl breast NEC (ICD10 C50.812)	Patients diagnosed with C50.812 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malign neopl breast NOS (ICD10 C50.919)	Patients diagnosed with C50.919 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malign neopl breast NOS (ICD10 C50.911)	Patients diagnosed with C50.911 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Malign neopl breast NOS (ICD10 C50.912)	Patients diagnosed with C50.912 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male nipple (ICD10 C50.029)	Patients diagnosed with C50.029 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male nipple (ICD10 C50.021)	Patients diagnosed with C50.021 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male nipple (ICD10 C50.022)	Patients diagnosed with C50.022 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.129)	Patients diagnosed with C50.129 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.121)	Patients diagnosed with C50.121 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.122)	Patients diagnosed with C50.122 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.329)	Patients diagnosed with C50.329 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.321)	Patients diagnosed with C50.321 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.322)	Patients diagnosed with C50.322 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.429)	Patients diagnosed with C50.429 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.421)	Patients diagnosed with C50.421 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.422)	Patients diagnosed with C50.422 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.529)	Patients diagnosed with C50.529 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.521)	Patients diagnosed with C50.521 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.522)	Patients diagnosed with C50.522 should be identified as male in their medical records.

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.629)	Patients diagnosed with C50.629 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.621)	Patients diagnosed with C50.621 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.622)	Patients diagnosed with C50.622 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.829)	Patients diagnosed with C50.829 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.821)	Patients diagnosed with C50.821 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.822)	Patients diagnosed with C50.822 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.929)	Patients diagnosed with C50.929 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.921)	Patients diagnosed with C50.921 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and diagnosis	Mal neo male breast NEC (ICD10 C50.922)	Patients diagnosed with C50.922 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 37788	Patients diagnosed with code 37788 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 76815	Patients diagnosed with code 76815 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 76825	Patients diagnosed with code 76825 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 76826	Patients diagnosed with code 76826 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 76827	Patients diagnosed with code 76827 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 76828	Patients diagnosed with code 76828 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 78761	Patients diagnosed with code 78761 should be identified as male in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 99500	Patients diagnosed with code 99500 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 19318	Patients diagnosed with code 19318 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code 19342	Patients diagnosed with code 19342 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code A4281	Patients diagnosed with code A4281 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code A4282	Patients diagnosed with code A4282 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code A4283	Patients diagnosed with code A4283 should be identified as female in their medical records.

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code A4284	Patients diagnosed with code A4284 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code A4285	Patients diagnosed with code A4285 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code A4286	Patients diagnosed with code A4286 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code E0602	Patients diagnosed with code E0602 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code E0603	Patients diagnosed with code E0603 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code E0604	Patients diagnosed with code E0604 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Gender and procedure	CPT code G0101	Patients diagnosed with code G0101 should be identified as female in their medical records.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Death indicator - death date	If there is a value or death_indcator, then there should be a death date in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Death_indicator - death_date	If there is no death_indicator, then there should not be a death date in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Cigarettes_indicator - tobacco use indicator	If there is a cigarettes_indicator, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Cigars_indicator - tobacco use indicator	If there is a cigars_indicator, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Chew_indicator - tobacco use indicator	If there is a chew_indicator, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Pipes_indicator - tobacco use indicator	If there is a pipes_indicator, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Snuff_indicator - tobacco use indicator	If there is a snuff_indicator, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Smokeless_tobacco_use_indicator - tobacco use indicator	If there is a smokeless_tobacco_use_indicator, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Smoking_tobacco_use_indicator - tobacco use indicator	If there is a smoking_tobacco_use_indicator, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Smoking_cessation_counseling_date - tobacco use indicator	If there is a smoking_cessation_counseling_date, then there should be a tobacco use indicator in the medical record.
1	Consistency	Relational	Common sense	Alcohol_use_details - alcohol use indicator	If there is a alcohol_use_details indicator, then there should be an alcohol use indicator.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Lamisil	If the patient is prescribed lamisil, then there should be an associated lab test entry for ALT.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Lamisil	If the patient is prescribed lamisil, then there should be an associated lab test entry for AST.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Lamisil	If the patient is prescribed lamisil, then there should be an associated lab test entry for GGT.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Methotrexate	If the patient is prescribed methotrexate, then there should be an associated lab test entry for Albumin.

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Methotrexate	If the patient is prescribed methotrexate, then there should be an associated lab test entry for Creatine.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Methotrexate	If the patient is prescribed methotrexate, then there should be an associated lab test entry for ALT
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Methotrexate	If the patient is prescribed methotrexate, then there should be an associated lab test entry for AST.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Methotrexate	If the patient is prescribed methotrexate, then there should be an associated lab test entry for GGT.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Prednisone	If the patient is prescribed prednisone, then there should be an associated lab test entry for GLU.
1	Completeness	Relational	Drug and lab results	Prednisone	If the patient is prescribed prednisone, then there should be an associated lab test entry for HbA1c.
1	Completeness	Relational	Diagnosis and lab results	Diabetes	If the patient is diagnosed with diabetes, then there should be an associated lab entry for GLU.
1	Completeness	Relational	Diagnosis and lab results	Diabetes	If the patient is diagnosed with diabetes, then there should be an associated lab entry for HbA1c.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Allergy drug - allergy	If the patient is prescribed an allergy drug, then their should be an allergy in their record.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Demographics - social history	If there is a demographic record for a patient, their social history information should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Demographics - contact information	If there is a demographic record for a patient, their contact information should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Demographics - encounters	If there is a demographic record for a patient, their encounter information should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Demographics - patient medical history	If there is a demographic record for a patient, their medical history should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Demographics - immunization	If there is a demographic record for a patient, their immunization information should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Demographics - vital	If there is a demographic record for a patient, their vital sign information should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Demographics - family medical history	If there is a demographic record for a patient, their family medical history should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Procedure - demographics	If there is a procedure record for a patient, their demographics should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Allergy - demographics	If there is an allergy record for a patient, their demographics should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Laboratory - demographics	If there is laboratory record for a patient, their demographics should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Diagnosis - demographics	If there is a diagnosis for a patient, their demographics should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Relational	Common sense	Hospitalization - demographics	If there is a hospitalization record for a patient, their demographics should also be complete.
1	Completeness	Value	Common sense	Patient ID	PatientID is not null
1	Completeness	Value	Common sense	Gender	Gender is not null

Source number	Dimension	Subdimension	Category	Class	Data Quality Check
1	Completeness	Value	Common sense	Day of birth	Day of birth is not null
1	Completeness	Value	Common sense	Day of diagnosis	Day of diagnose is not null
1	Completeness	Value	Common sense	Diagnosis	Diagnosis is not null
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	T Category	When the T category is specified as Tis, the corresponding stage must be classified as stage 0.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	T Category	For T categories T0, T1, and T3: - T0 must be paired with N1 and M0 for stage IIA. - T1 can be paired with N0 and M0 for stage I, or with N1 and M0 for stage IIA. - T3 must be paired with N0 and M0 for stage IIB, or with N1/N2 and M0 for stage IIIA.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	T Category	When the T categyory is T4, the corresponding stage must be classified as stage IIIB.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	T Category	For stages IIIC and IV: - For stage IIIC, any T category is acceptable when paired with N3 and M0. - For stage IV, and T category is acceptable when paired with any N category and M1.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	N Category	When the N category is specified as N0, the stage van be classified as 0, I, IIA, IIB, or IIIB.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	N Category	When the N category is N1, the stage can be classified as IIA, IIB, or IIIB.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	N Category	When the N category is N2, the corresponding stage must be IIIA or IIIB.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	N Category	When the N category is N3, the stage must be classified as IIIC.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	M Category	When the M category is M0, the stage can range from 0 to IIIC.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	M Category	When the M category is M1, the cancer must be classified as stage IV, independedent of T and N categories.
4	Consistency	Relational	Staging data and stage grouping	T Category	When the T category is specified as Tis, the corresponding stage must be classified as stage 0.

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